

The Excel spreadsheet contains 14 data types for each sample, including porosity, density, V_{om} , V_{QFP} , V_{CL} , V_{CRB} , V_p0 , V_s0 , epsilon and gamma. V_{om} is the volume fraction of organic matter in the rock matrix. V_{QFP} denotes the total volume content of quartz, feldspar, and pyrite in the rock matrix. V_{CL} and V_{CRB} denote the total clay content and carbonate content, including calcite and dolomite, in the rock matrix. Note that the sum of V_{om} , V_{QFP} , V_{CL} , and V_{CRB} equals unity. V_p0 represents the P-wave velocity propagating perpendicular to the shale bedding. V_s0 denotes the vertical S-wave velocity. Epsilon denotes the P-wave anisotropic parameter. Gamma denotes the S-wave anisotropic parameter. Specifically, these anisotropic parameters can be expressed by stiffness coefficients:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{C_{11} - C_{33}}{2C_{33}} \quad (1-1)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{C_{66} - C_{44}}{2C_{44}} \quad (1-2)$$

Many papers give TOC rather than kerogen volume fraction. We convert the mass fraction of TOC to the organic matter volume fraction in the matrix through (Vernik and Landis 1996)

$$V_{om} = \frac{TOC * \rho_m}{C_k * \rho_k} \quad (1-3)$$

where ρ_m is the matrix density, and ρ_k is the kerogen density. C_k is the carbon concentration in the solid organic matter. For immature shale, C_k and ρ_k are 75.00% and 1.126, respectively. For mature shale, C_k and ρ_k are 79.65% and 1.293, respectively. For overmature shale, C_k and ρ_k are 85.00% and 1.485, respectively.

The mineral composition of shale is quite complex, including quartz, feldspar, calcite, dolomite, and pyrite. Published papers give mineral content in mass fraction or volume fraction. We convert the mass fraction of mineral composition to the volume fraction through

$$V_q = \frac{M_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl}}{M_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_f * \rho_q * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_c * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_d * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_p * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_{cl} + M_{cl} * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p} \quad (1-4)$$

$$V_f = \frac{M_f * \rho_q * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl}}{M_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_f * \rho_q * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_c * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_d * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_p * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_{cl} + M_{cl} * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p} \quad (1-5)$$

$$V_c = \frac{M_c * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl}}{M_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_f * \rho_q * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_c * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_d * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_p * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_{cl} + M_{cl} * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p} \quad (1-6)$$

$$V_d = \frac{M_d * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_p * \rho_{cl}}{M_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_f * \rho_q * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_c * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_d * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_p * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_{cl} + M_{cl} * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p} \quad (1-7)$$

$$V_p = \frac{M_p * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_{cl}}{M_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_f * \rho_q * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_c * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_d * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_p * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_{cl} + M_{cl} * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p} \quad (1-8)$$

$$V_{cl} = \frac{M_{cl} * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p}{M_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_f * \rho_q * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_c * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_d * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_d * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_p * \rho_{cl} + M_p * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_{cl} + M_{cl} * \rho_q * \rho_f * \rho_c * \rho_d * \rho_p} \quad (1-9)$$

where M_q , M_f , M_c , M_d , M_p and M_{cl} are mass fractions of quartz, feldspar, calcite, dolomite, pyrite and clay, respectively. ρ_q , ρ_f , ρ_c , ρ_d , ρ_p and ρ_{cl} are densities of quartz, feldspar, calcite, dolomite, pyrite and clay, respectively. We normalized the kerogen volume fraction with the mineral volume fraction. Then V_{QFP} is the sum of quartz, feldspar, and pyrite contents. V_{CRB} is the sum of calcite and dolomite contents. The original mineral data from Vernik & Landis (1996) is the average mineral content. Longmaxi data (Liu et al., 2019), Niobrara data (Al-Khalifa, 2016) are extracted through image processing, so there may be some deviation from the original data